

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B144
 Date: 3 Dec 2005
 Take Off 11:58:41 Exeter
 Landing: 15:56:25 Exeter
 Flight Time 3h57m44

Campaign: MICROMIX
Operating Area: SW approaches

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Foster	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Steve Ball	FAAM
3	3 rd Pilot	Ian Ramsay-Rae	Directflight
4	CCM	Sue Angold	Directflight
5	Mission Scientist 1	Clare Lee	Met Office
6	Mission Scientist 2	Stuart Newman	Met Office
7	Flight Manager	Alan Woolley	FAAM
8	Drosondes/ CCM2	Doug Anderson	FAAM
9	Cloud Physics	Martyn Pickering	Met Office
10	MARSS/Deimos	Ian Rule	Met Office
11	SWS	Dave Kindred	Met Office
12	CPI	Ian Crawford	Manchester University
13	Mission Scientist Training	Peter Sheridan	Met Office
14			
15			
16			
17			
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19			

Flight Track:

B144 Track 03-DEC-05

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B144
 Date: 3 Dec 2005
 Project: MICROMIX
 Location: SW Approaches

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
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114428		inu to nav	0.85 kft	140	
114617		engine start	0.85 kft	140	
115251		taxy	0.86 kft	143	
115841		T/O	0.82 kft	256	from Exeter
120434		jw/nevz zero	11.4 kft	294	
120554		asp open	13.7 kft	261	
122450		BBR shutter retract	24.0 kft	275	
124156		jw nevz zero	24.0 kft	175	
124625	132141	Profile 1	24.0 - 0.86 kft	175	
124701		bbr extend	23.6 kft	175	
125849		Profile 1	11.0 kft	231	interrupt
130410		Profile 1	11.0 kft	335	resume
130956		Profile 1	4.9 kft	336	500 ft/min
131533		Profile 1	2.6 kft	336	interrupt
131721		Profile 1	2.6 kft	125	resume
131943		bbr retract	1.3 kft	133	
132141	132940	Run 1	0.86 - 0.84 kft	141	
133137	140338	Profile 2	0.85 - 24.0 kft	337	
133300		bbr extend	1.6 kft	337	
133452		Spiral start	2.6 kft	336	
133826		nevz stopped working	4.2 kft	134	
134117		Profile 2	5.5 kft	276	
134211		Profile 2	5.4 kft	276	resume
134326		Profile 2	6.0 kft	324	1000ft/min
134921		Profile 2	12.0 kft	275	interrupt
135008		Profile 2	12.0 kft	277	resume
135530		Profile 2	17.0 kft	167	interrupt
135619		Profile 2	17.0 kft	180	resume
140422	140650	Profile 3	24.3 - 26.0 kft	110	
140929	141928	Run 2.1	26.0 kft	344	
141016		bbr retract	26.0 kft	343	
141058		sonde 1	26.0 kft	342	launch
142304	143307	Run 2.2	26.0 kft	158	
142923		sonde 2	26.0 kft	158	launch
143625	152414	Profile 4	26.0 - 1.6 kft	338	interrupt
143655		Profile 4	25.6 kft	348	is a spiral
144216		Profile 4	19.8 kft	178	interrupt
144320		Profile 4	19.9 kft	175	resume
144606		bbr extend	17.3 kft	278	
144834		Profile 4	15.1 kft		interrupt
145015		Profile 4	15.0	030	resume
145625		Profile 4	9.0 kft	286	interrupt
145912		Profile 4	8.9 kft	288	resume
150202		Profile 4	6.5 kft	047	interrupt
150827		Profile 4	6.5 kft	158	resume
151033		Profile 4	4.5 kft	156	500ft/min
151526		Profile 4	1.6 kft	153	interrupt
152246		Profile 4	1.6 kft	073	resume
152422	153217	Run 3	0.85 - 0.89 kft	070	
152802		bbr retract	0.90 kft	077	
154005		asp closed	5.5 kft	340	
155625		Land	0.78 kft	255	at Exeter
160305		standstill	0.80 kft	145	50'43.91N, 3'24.95W

Sortie Brief

MICROMIX

Flight: B144

Date: 3rd December 2005

Trial Objectives:

To characterise the microphysics of mixed phase cloud and atmospheric state in conjunction with an AMSU overpass for validating radiative transfer models.

Location:

A region of mixed phase cloud anticipated to be SW approaches which will coincide with an AMSU overpasses at 13:33, 14:59 (and 12:46).

Weather:

'Reasonably' homogenous mixed phase cloud.

Flight Pattern:

Deep spiral ascent/descent advecting with the air mass.

	Start time	Manoeuvre	Time for flight segment	Total time
1	12:00	Take off and transit at FL240	20	40
2	12:20	Profile descent to 50ft into operating area	30	
3	12:50	1 x10 min straight and level run along sub-satellite track at 100ft	10	50
4	13:00	Spiral ascent to 1000ft above cloud top initially at 500 ft/min, increasing to 1000ft/min above the boundary layer advecting with the wind.	30	90
5	13:30	Two 10min reciprocal runs along the sub-satellite track at 1000ft above cloud. Dropping one or two sondes. Satellite overpass 13:33	25	110
6	13:55	Spiral descent to min. alt. initially at 1000 ft/min, decreasing to 500ft/min below the boundary layer advecting with the wind.	30	160
7	14:25	1 x 10 min run along sub-satellite track at 100ft	10	180
8	14:35	Profile ascent to freezing layer	5	
9	14:40	2 x 10 min straight and level runs at freezing layer. Satellite overpass 14:59 .	25	
10	15:05	Profile ascent to 3000ft above freezing layer	3	

11	15:08	2 x 10 min straight and level runs.	25	
12	15:33	Profile descent to 50ft	12	
13	15:45	1 x 10 min Run along sub-satellite track at 100ft	10	
14	15:55	Profile ascent from 50ft to max alt within operating area	45	
15	16:40	Transit to Exeter	20	220
16	17:00	Land Exeter		

Runs and profiles to be conducted at 200 KIAS.

Clearances:

Clearances will be required for flying at low levels and possibly for dropping sondes.

B144 – Mission Scientist De-brief
3rd Dec 2005
Dr Clare Lee

The aim of the sortie was to study mixed phase clouds over the SW approaches. The weather situation was a band of mixed phase cloud moving Eastwards with cloud tops at approx FL220, which unfortunately started to dissipate towards the end of the sortie, as well as moving into restricted air traffic areas and hence the flight was terminated earlier than planned. No contrails were observed during the whole of the sortie.

Note, that during the flight several attempts to use the sat phone failed either totally or shortly after speaking to a forecaster for a few seconds. An infrared satellite image update was therefore impossible during the flight.

Take off was at 12:00 as planned from Exeter. There were light showers during pre-flight, which could have contributed to noise problems with the 2DC, which persisted during the whole flight. Later it was identified to be due to some dirt which was not present at the pre-flight checks of the probe.

The transit to the operating area was made in a direction towards a point identified by the pilots on the FIA boarder. The mixed phase cloud was not found at that location as anticipated on an earlier satellite image, and hence turned South along the FIA boarder to an appropriate cloud. This increase in transit meant that the first satellite overpass occurred whilst the aircraft was performing the spiral descent.

A profile descent was made into the cloud with tops at FL230, though highly variable. The descent was interrupted to stay within the bulk of the cloud. Below 3000ft there was precipitation intermittently. The low level run was restricted to 250 ft due to the pilots. Performed a spiral ascent at banking angle of 10 degrees, which was interrupted for short times for the gyros to stabilise. Mixture of ice and liquid water seen from 4000ft to FL165. Clouds tops from FL198 to FL230. Profile ascent to FL260 to ensure the aircraft was above clouds and allow for the dropsonde to stabilise before reaching the cloud.. A straight and level run (2) was made above the cloud top at FL260 and a sonde dropped at 141058. A reciprocal run (2.2) was made, with the sonde dropped when over the bulk of the cloud again at 142923.

A spiral descent at banking angle of 10 degrees was made, again interrupted for the gyros and also to maintain descent in the cloud. At this time the cloud was starting to dissipate and move further East which required further air traffic clearance. At 1000ft it was necessary to maintain altitude and location whilst the pilots negotiated airspace clearance. The profile was recommenced to follow the cloud down to 250ft. a run was made at 250ft, but it was clear that the cloud had dissipated too much and the science flight was terminated early.

Instrument status

MARSS – OK

Deimos –OK – display was working normally

SWS – OK (training flight)

CPI – crashed several times throughout the flight and had some difficulty restarting within the cloud. Good data otherwise.

Cloud Physics – All OK except at high altitude and 2DC

2DC – noisy data due to dirt on probe

UFC – pre-flight had a failure, but worked OK after heated.

DFC – failed in flight (used SWS camera for recording downward views)

Nevz – stopped working after 1338

Turbulence probes – acting strangely from 1430 during spiral descent

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Mission Scientist

Flight No **B.144**
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Date **3.1.2.105**

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
12:00					T10 Exeter
					Exeter weather passing showers - drizzle, 719 W initially UTC VIS after heater on → OK.
12:08					3D reporting problems with water still on probe, making it noisy. Thought that at low level it will clear up.
12:14		FL240	277	50.8/4.9	Cloud tops FL220 tops → FL240 StW.
					Heading towards pt. A (border of FIA).
12:31:27					W lower, wispiness above.
					N.B. DFC malfunctioning asked for FCC, RFE.
					Can see clear patches ahead.
123652		FL240	178	50.8/7.6	left turn to find appropriate cloud, S along FIA border.
124033		FL240	175	50.5/7.6	419 W.
124625	P1	FL240	175	50.0/7.4	Profile
12 4744		FL231			Top of cloud.

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Mission Scientist

Flight No **B**.....144.....
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Date 3/12/05.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
1247	✓	FL230			CPI starting to see.
		FL226	175	49.8/17.3	Now seeing small ice response. T -36.54, T _D -36.63 FSSP seeing gel. high concn. variable cloud top wind 18 ms ⁻¹ / 257°
125220					slight roll to right to head towards weather on the radar. (corner to of FIA + Prest borders).
125353		FL161			CPI large ice crystals ~140/12
125658		FL120			CPI seeing columns. T -13.0, T _D -11.68
125849	Plint	FL110	230		Profile 1 intercept. left turn. Can see sea below.
		FL110	134	49.1/17.7	Leading towards thicker cloud. still hazy.
130114		FL110	41	49.1/17.5	in thicker cloud.
130215					CPI just crashed maintaining level until restarted. wind 20ms ⁻¹ / 262°
					CPI having difficulty restarting.
130410	Pl sl	FL110	337	49.3/17.5	Recommence profile descent.

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Mission Scientist

Flight No **B144**.....

Date **3/12/05**.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
130503					Thick to right, patchy to left can see through to sea occasionally.
130534					In cloud. 2D was still having nose problems.
		FL 708			T-5.84, T _D -6.07
130915		15000ft	335		T-2.31 T _D -2.39 variable cloud below.
1309					500ft/min.
		3920			T-0.45, T _D 0.7
					2D seeing water drops + ice.
					in and out of cloud.
1312:00		2970			CPI still won't reboot. raining.
		2670	336	49.9/1.8	T 1.4, T _D 1.89.
131444		2380			Still raining. Coming out of cloud.
131533	PI int.	2000ft.			turning right to get back into cloud.
131721	PI	2000ft.	123	30.0/1.7	Recommencing profile to 2500ft. T 5.6, T _D 2.84.
131930			140		Raining again, much harder. wind 19 1290

✱

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Mission Scientist

Flight No **B.144**

Date **3/12/05**

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
132104		290	141	49.8/7.4	Rain stopped.
132141	} Plnd. } R1st.	250ft.	140		
		250ft.	156		Run at 250ft. Definitely below cloud.
132417					Rain again. FTC ok again. - being recorded.
					T ₁ +9.1, T ₂ +7.8
132737					Hermann cal. ^(SST=11.80) under reading by.
132815		250ft.	168	49.4/7.1	Clear to right, thicker W to left. Raining intermittently.
132940	Plnd.				End of rain. left hand turn.
133137	Pl	250ft	335	49.4/6.9	Straight profile, initially to get into cloud
		1500		49.5/7.0	wind 15 ms ⁻¹ 1280°
133452		2000		49.6/7.0	banking at 10° for spiral ascent
		3210			heavy heavy rain. 2D had a slightly melted look. T 2.3, T ₂ 2.8.
133735					Near TWC has just gone UIS
133754		4030			2D looks like ice with water

CPL on line again.

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Mission Scientist

Flight No **B.144**.....

Date **3/12/05**.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
133840		FL400 4200			CPL seeing ice particles.
133910		4440	174	49.6/16.7	CPL seeing very large ice. Meseros. dead. still, can see patchy cloud below. (see wave crests)
134117	P2int.	5450	278	49.5/16.8	Intercept spiral as V1H having difficulty. dear slot to left.
134210	P2st.	5490	297	49.5/16.9	Recommencing spiral turn to right.
134315		6000			increasing to 1000ft./min T-2.4, T _D -4.46. wind 18ms ⁻¹ / 269°
134450		7980			2D seeing large aggregates. FSSP indicating small water drops CPL seeing aggregates + some pressure plates. T -7.99, T _D -7.71°
134631		9400		49.6/16.7	CPL seeing columns. mainly + mixture.
134722		FL100		49.5/16.7	small turbulence. T-11.31, T _D -11.5
134915	P2int.	FL120		49.5/16.8	Spiral interrupted to get gyros back.
135008	P2st.	FL120	290	49.5/16.8	Recommence spiral.

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Mission Scientist

Flight No **B**.....144.....

Date 3/12/05.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
135056		FL170		49.6/69	CPI plates + mixture 2D larger aggregates FSSP possibility of some liquid water? - v. small quantities. T -16.45, T _D -17.28 wind 17 ms ⁻¹ / 258°
135453		FL165			aircraft with ice on i.e. still liquid water + FSSP ^{seeing} _{increase of} ^{fruit} level.
135530	P2 _{int}	FL170			interrupting spiral
135619	P2 _{st}	FL170			recommence prof't spiral
135902		FL198		49.4/67	Reaching tops of clud.
140127		FL217		49.5/68	still in clud. -variable clud tops.
140230		FL230			above cluds.
140338		FL240	162		
140422	P3	FL240			recommence to get to alt/so with 10° roll to right. ^{drop} _{samples} ⁱⁿ _{capture} ^{all} _{clud.}
140650	P3 _{end}	FL260	198	49.5/62	turning right for straight + levels above clud. along sub orbital direction.
14:09:29	R2	FL260	342	49.5/64	250 67 drift. clud looks thick all around
14:10:58	S1	FL260	342	49.7/64	drops and l. wind 27ms ⁻¹ / 271° sonde ok. + intermittent winds

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Mission Scientist

Flight No **B.144**.....

Date **3/12/05**.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
141610		FL260			2DC still v. noisy will only see v. large particles 2DP doesn't work at this alt.
141814		FL260	338	50.3/6.6	Cloud thinning + clearing ahead.
141938	R2ad				End of run. turning right on to reciprocal over 18 W.
142304	R2.2	FL260	158	50.5/6.5	Start of reciprocal run. T-45.8, T _D -58.68
142638				50.1/6.2	Heading back over the cloud. T-44.43, T _D -58.73
					No contrails: Engine settings N ₁ = 82.4, TGT = 62 N ₂ 84.3, FF/FO
142923	S2	FL260	158	50.0/6.1	Drop sonde 2. looks OK, inc. winds. will go ~ 10 miles East.
143307	R2.2ad	FL260		49.6/5.8	turning right for reciprocal heading
143625	P4st	FL260		49.7/6.0	Spiral profile descent. DP bank turning to right.
133858		FL232			CP seeing particles + drop sonde landed.

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Mission Scientist

Flight No **B.144**.....

Date **3/12/05**.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
144045		FL213		50.0/5.6	Maybe catching bird
144206	P4 int	FL200		49.8/5.5	intercept
144320	P4 st	FL200			Recommence
144834	P4 int	FL150		49.8/5.7	intercept
					T-19.9, T _D -20.25
145015	P4 st	FL150			Recommence to right
					maybe came out of cloud
					slightly during straight + level
					section for stabilisation
145158		FL132		50.0/5.4	In clear
					2D not seeing any cloud
145354		FL113		49.9/5.2	Heading into cloud. 4/8 W below
145442					2D seeing larger aggregates again
145625	P4 int	FL90		49.8/5.4	intercept
					seem to be below extensive
					cloud, at of mixed phase phase
					T-7.4, T _D -16.22
145912	P4 st	FL90		49.8/5.6	Recommence descent
1459					overpass now!
					not in mixed phase cloud
		6500ft			
150202		6500ft			T-3.17, T _D -9.95
					still at of cloudy
					into patchy stuff only
					Have requested to go into
					Plymouth area.

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Mission Scientist

Flight No **B.144**.....

Date **3/12/05**.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
150815		6500ft		49.9/5.3	Leading towards cloud which has gone SE.
150851					In cloud.
150827	P4st	6500ft			Recognition P4 hit on straight + level. (1000ft/min)
1510		5000ft			changing to 500ft/min N.B. Turbulence probes acting strangely from ~2:30 during spiral descent.
151155		3600	154	49.7/5.1	T 2.28, TD -1.0 Wind 21ms ⁻¹ 275°
151243		2450	154	49.6/5.0	betting below mixed phase cloud. Some turbulence
151526	P4 id.	1000ft.			intercept as coming across FIA boundary. Leading left to catch cloud, but need to go up + down boundary to maintain cloud.
151758					turning left whilst checking high areas we can go into. (bank 10°) T 7.3, TD 3.97
151928		1000ft	131	44.5/4.7	some turbulence, below mixed phase cloud again.

B1443/12/05.10/10152246 P4st. 100ft. 72 ^{49.5}/₄₃

Recommencing profile descent.

Still negotiating operating area with air traffic.

Wind 20ms⁻¹ 1266°T+8.87°, T_D+4.32°

152414 P4end 250ft. 69 49.61

152422 R3st. ⁴/₂

Some turbulence leading to below mixed phase cloud.

152643

Raining

Cloud becoming v. patchy mixed phase cloud heading S over French border. No other systems close by, except scattered Cu.

SST 12.4 Heimann, looking close to real.

153217 R4end 250ft. ^{49.7}/_{3.4}

End of low level run.

Heading back, as no sensible cloud.

CPI won't restart.

Transit back to Exeter.

Cloud thickening towards land.

Last instrument status.

MARSS OK

Deimos OK. - were seeing BT's on screen.

Cloud Physics 2DP at high alt. vis.

RDC noisy.

SIDI OK.

FASP OK. except high alt.

CPI crashed 3 times, but otherwise OK.

SWS all OK.

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 144

Date: 3/12/05	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 10:42:55	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time:	Page 1 of 3
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
12:27:00																Both 2D2-C and P on rearm 1	
12:46:25	Noise		62			Noise		Noise								Start Profile 1 from FL240	
12:47:40	Noise		63	100		Noise		Noise								FL230	
12:48:50	Noise		64	200		Noise		Noise								FL220	
12:49:40	Noise		66	100		Noise		Noise								FL210	
12:50:25	Noise		67	100		Noise		Noise								FL200	
12:51:19	Noise		69	50		Noise		Noise								FL190	
12:52:16	Noise			100		Noise		Noise								FL180	
12:53:05	Noise		71	100		Noise		17000	1400						8	FL170	
12:54:05	Noise		77	100		Noise		9000	1400						8	FL160	
12:55:10	Noise		78	100		400		14000	1000						8	FL150	
12:56:05	Noise		87	1000		300	800	50000	1000						8	FL140	
12:57:10	Noise		114	1200		2000	800	65000	4000						2	FL130	
12:58:49	Noise		151	10		90	800	175	2000						8	FL110 rearm 1 and 2 to normal	
13:04:57	Noise		223	10		145	800	1000	1200						8	FL100	
13:05:55	Noise		226	5		200	800	2000	1400						8	FL090	
13:07:11	Noise		227	10		440	800	2900	1000						6	FL080	
13:08:02	Noise		228	5		Noise		75								FL070	
13:08:38	Noise			5												FL060	
13:09:45	10	0.07		10		20	800	70000	400						1	FL050	
13:11:50	200	0.20	243	1000		260	800	50000	800						1	FL040	
13:14:36	35	0.10	255	10		80	400	1700	400						1	FL030	
13:18:06	10	0.11	256	5				200	1600						1	FL020	
13:21:24	20	0.11	259													End of Profile 1 @ 250'	
13:21:40																Start Run 1 @ 250'	
13:22:00	15	0.11	260	50				8									
13:24:00	15	0.10		100		3	600	180	800						1		
13:26:00	35	0.13	262	80		3	600	225	600						1		
13:28:00	40	0.21	264	90		75	800	3400	4000						1		
13:29:40																End of Run 1	
13:31:37	310	0.17	268	90		1	500	500	1200						1	Start Profile 2 from 250'	
13:33:55	20	0.08	270	20		15	800	375	400						1	FL020	
13:35:40	125	0.17	278	1000		100	800	65	600						1	FL030	
13:38:08	40	0.13	294	40		135	375	800	3000						8	FL040	
13:40:14	50	0.22	299	100		200	800	4500	4000						8	FL050	
13:43:22	5	0.07	308	10		35	25	110	2000						8	FL060	
13:44:29	10	0.11														FL070	
13:45:45	100	0.23	328	1000		2000	800	50000	5000						8	FL080	
13:47:15	1000	0.33	379	700		660	800	9700	2400						8	FL100	
13:48:25	50	0.37	387	100		700	600	11000	1800						8	FL110	
13:49:27	50	0.21	394	200		1700	600	13000	2000						8	FL120	
13:51:30	55	0.13	412	200		1600	600	15000	1000						8	FL130	
13:52:38	95	0.14	416	100		2100	500	16000	600						8	FL140	
13:53:50	320	0.35	428	1000		4600	775	10000	2400						8	FL150	
13:54:50	2500	0.31	504			Noise										FL160	
13:55:45	400	0.28	527	100		Noise										FL170	

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 144

Date: 3/12/05	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 10:42:55	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time:	Page 2 of 3
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
13:57:44	1000	0.10	533	100		Noise		90	200						11	FL180	
13:59:35	100	0.06	537	10		Noise		250	200						11	FL200 rearm 1 1	
14:01:25	300	0.07	539	1000		Noise		6000	200						11	FL220	
14:03:18	210	0.06	542			Noise										FL240	
14:04:00	Noise					Noise										Start Profile 3 from FL240	
14:06:50	Noise					Noise										End of Profile 3 @ FL260 rearm 2 1	
14:09:26																Start Run 2.1 @ FL260	
14:10:00	Noise					Noise		Noise									
14:12:00	Noise					Noise		Noise									
14:14:00	Noise					Noise		Noise									
14:16:00	Noise					Noise		Noise									
14:18:00	Noise					Noise		Noise									
14:19:28																End of Run 2.1	
14:23:07																Start Run 2.2 @ FL260	
14:24:00	Noise					Noise		Noise									
14:26:00	Noise					Noise		Noise									
14:28:00	Noise					Noise		Noise									
14:30:00	Noise					Noise		Noise									
14:32:00	Noise					Noise		Noise									
14:33:07																End of Run 2.2	
14:36:26	Noise					Noise		Noise								Start Profile 4 from FL260	
14:38:25	Noise		543	1000		Noise		Noise								FL240	
14:39:19	Noise		544	300		Noise		Noise								FL230	
14:40:20	Noise		546	700		Noise		Noise								FL220	
14:41:03	Noise		548	800		Noise	800	Noise							8	FL210	
14:42:05	Noise		555	100		Noise		Noise								FL200	
14:44:21	Noise		556	10		Noise		Noise								FL190	
14:45:20	Noise			10		Noise	400	Noise							8	FL180	
14:46:20	Noise		557	800		Noise	700	30000	800						8	FL170 rearm 2	
14:47:30	Noise		562	600		800	600	11000	800						8	FL160	
14:48:39	Noise		563	100		400	400	1500	1600						8	FL150 rearm 1 64	
14:51:19	200	0.15	565	100		300	250	700	400						11	FL140	
14:52:10	5	0.06				Noise										FL130	
14:53:05	4	0.06				Noise										FL120	
14:54:19	8	0.06	566	10		100	400	125	1000						8	FL110	
14:55:19	16	0.15		10		35	200									FL100	
14:56:25	5	0.08		5		30	600	200	1000						8	FL090	
15:00:10	5	0.09														FL080	
15:02:08	5	0.08				Noise										FL065	
15:08:55	140	0.15	586	1000		4	300	10								FL060	
15:10:03	20	0.08	587	10		Noise										FL050	
15:11:12	17	0.08		10		Noise										FL040	
15:12:49	25	0.09		80		Noise										FL030	
15:14:37	20	0.09		10		40	700	50	600						1	FL020	
15:24:14	30	0.09	588	20		Noise										End of Profile 4 Start Run 3 @ 250'	
15:25:00	25	0.07		10		Noise											

CLLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B144

Date: 03/12/2005

A) FFSSP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Transfer *.txt files from DVD to PC B144_FFSSP_hh.txt for each hour of data B144_FFSSP_HVMS.txt		
2) FTP the files (ascii) from the PC to the directory PMSDATA: on FLOODS	23/12/05	
3) RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FFSSP]FFSSP_EXTRACT_TAS a) Flight number: B144 b) Path name: MFDDATA:B144_MFDX c) Output directory: PMSDATA: d) Start time: 0 if unknown e) End time: 240000 if unknown	23/12/05	
4) RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FFSSP]FFSSP_PROCESS_TXT a) Flight number: B144 b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) TAS in processing: Y d) Vel threshold (clicks) 0 e) Calibration file: Use the most recent calibration file. Format FFSSP_CALddmmyyyy.txt Calibration files to be stored in MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FFSSP] f) Adjust FFSSP time Y/N g) If Y, enter value to add to data time (seconds)	0 n 23/12/05	Note the calibration file used FFSSP_CAL19112005.TXT Yes only if gross errors occur in FFSSP time eg; ~ 1hour complete
5) In PVWAVE a) enter: !path=!path+',mrfb:[pms.proc]' Note that the comma before "mrfb" is important! b) write_procffssp_to_m5,'pmsdata:B144_procffssp.dat', 'mfddata:B144_mfdX','pmsdata:B144_m5procffssp' 1st argument is output file from 5) 2nd argument is the MFD 3rd argument is the new FFSSP data file in M5 format c) exit	23/12/05	Note the correction applied to FFSSP time by /auto No auto-time-correction
6) MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:B144_m5procffssp b) Datset: mfddata:B144_mfdX c) New dataset: Enter updated MFD name d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default	23/12/05	complete
7) CHECKS:		
i) FFSSP and JW/Nevzorov LWC – are they correctly synchronized in time?		Time-synch looks OK
ii) If not, may be necessary to repeat 5b) using addt=x keyword. This adds x sec to FFSSP time.		

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG**Flight number:** B144**Date:** 03/12/2005

B) 2D PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Transfer B144.dat file from CD/DVD to PC		
2) Zip up file on PC (B144.zip)		
3) FTP the zipped file (binary) from the PC to the directory SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] on FLOODS		
4) Log on to FLOODS		
5) unzip SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]B144.zip		
6) In PVWAVE i) !PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]' ii) CONVERT_SEADAS_FILE a) Input file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]B144.dat b) Output file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]B144_seadas.dat iii) exit	23/12/05	Note the number of bad block reads and/or final numbers of blocks read & written 85829 blocks read / written No errors
7) run MRFB:[PMS.SEADAS]READM200_FILE a) Default directory: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: B144 c) Disk file name: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]B144_seadas.dat d) Comment string: e) Start time: 0 if unknown f) End time: 240000 if unknown g) Read 2DC: Y h) Read 2DP: Y i) Secondary data: Y j) FSP-SYNC: Y k) cmd.str: Y l) Auto time correction: N m) Full length secondary: N	115900 155600	Data ends ~154100
8) 2D image display and printing Quick look at image blocks if required In PVWAVE i) !PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]' ii) WAVE> IMAGEDISPLAY a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: B144 c) IWC plot: N d) Select probe: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP e) Start time: 0 if unknown f) End time: 240000 if unknown g) Time interval (sec): 0 for every image block nominal 5 sec		This section is optional Features to look for: 1) Noise on 2D-P – does it affect non-edge diodes (with potential to create spurious particle counts)? 2) Can you identify a dominant particle habit for the whole flight (eg. drops or crystals) 3)

Preparation of imagery for Core data product		
iii) WAVE> auto_image a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: B144 c) Enter date: YYYYMMDD d) Enter start time 0 if unknown e) Enter end time 240000 if unknown f) Enter time interval (sec) between successive imaged blocks 10 iv) exit PVWAVE Creates files	115900 155600 10 PMSDATA:	Noise throughout on 2DC – single pixels which may not get rejected. Some periods of well-formed images hence refer to image file for periods of reliability of processed data. Ditto 2DP FAAM_YYYYMMDD_R0_B144_2Dx-IMAGES.PS
ftp *.PS files from PMSDATA: to PC		
Load each into Ghostview or other pdf-converter		
Output as pdf file (70 dpi resolution) and append name prefix of CORE-CLOUD-PHY_ to converted files		
9) run MRFB:[PMS.SPEC2D.AUTO]PROCESS2D_AUTO		
a) Flight number: B144 b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) File generation: Hit enter d) Time correction: Time offset of the 2D data e) TAS: Y f) MFD directory: MFDDATA:B144_MFDX g) Probe number: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP (0) Both 0 unless either probe known to be faulty h) Start time: 0 if unknown i) End time: 240000 if unknown j) Nominal averaging: 0.2 seconds for conversion to M5 k) Particle type: 8 if known to be in ice cloud 11 if known to be in water cloud 8 if known to be in mixed-phase 8 if unknown l) Coefficient choice: 2 m) Output root filename: PMSDATA:B144_PROC2D	120020 154200 23/12/05	If program crashes at a certain Time, for any reason, re-run With that time as the new end. Note problem with iced-up AoSS port – affects centre-port TAS particularly between about 143000 and 150100 Note the particle type complete
10) In PVWAVE		
i) enter: !PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]' Note that the comma before "mrfb" is important! ii) WRITE_PROC2D_TO_M5, 'PMSDATA:B144_PROC2D.DAT', 'PMSDATA:B144_M5PROC2D' iii) exit		
11) MODIFY		
a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:B144_m5proc2D b) Datset: mfddata:B144_mfdX c) New dataset: Enter modified MFD name d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default	23/12/05	
12) CHECKS:		
i) Is 2DC/2DP IWC of comparable magnitude and well-correlated with Nevzorov TWC?		Noise dominated 2DC for much of flight – only a few short

		periods are OK. Much 2DP noise rejected – some cloud passes 1330-1400 look OK. Also 1245-1315

* TRAINING FLIGHT. (DLK) SWS LOG *

SWS FLIGHT LOG SHEET

Flight #	B 144	Date	3/12/05	Operator(s)	DLK (V/T) (DLK)	log page	1	of	4
Time	Run id	Alt/FL	Mirr Pos	Int Times		Remarks			
				Vis	NIR				

112515	Pre-	—	↓	500	1000	SWS running	} checked out running then stopped (x2) pre-flight		
112941	Flight.	—	↓	500	1000	SWS stopped Camera ↓ mirror to protect from rain showers passing by.			
115242				←		Start Taxi @ Exeter.			
115845				←		T/O Exeter (Rotated SWS wheel ↓ to → once rolling)			
120000		↗	Rear	500	1000	Start current view	(SWS Temp +11°C)		
120029	Transit	4.3kft	Rear.	500	1000	Start measurement			
120222						Start ^{dark} current view			
120255	"	9.0kft	↑*	200	1000	Start measurement	* 6° OFFSET APPLIED		
120351						Start dark current view			
120419	"	11.5kft	↑*	350	500	Start measurement			
120544	"		↑	350	1000	Start measurement to NIR.			
120833		↗				Start dark current view			
120856	Transit	18.8kft	↓*	350	750	Start measurement	* 6° OFFSET APPLIED		
121001						Start dark current view			
121031	Transit	↗	↓*	150	750	Start measurement			
121143	"	↗	↓*			Start measurement (SWS Temp +13°C)			
121248	"	↗	↓*	50	500	Start measurement (Peltiers on 1, 2 ; 3 & 4)			
123622						START CAMERA RECORDING (LP) (TEMP +11°C)			
123804		FL				Start Dark View (Temp +11°C)			
123831	Transit	240.	↓*	250	1000	Start Measurement Peltier 340N; 1 & 2 OFF			
124625	↓ P1	FL240	↓*	250	1000	Start Desert P1			
124734						Start Dark View * 6° OFFSET			
124802			↓*	400	750	Start Measurement APPLIED			
124831				100	750	Start Dark View			
124851	P1 ↓	FL210	↓*	100	750	Start Measurement			
125022						Start Dark View (Temp +11°C)			
125044	P1 ↓	FL19.6	↓*	50	750	Start Measurement (Good spectra)			

VN

SWS FLIGHT LOG SHEET

Flight #	B 144	Date	3/12/05	Operator(s)	JDK (ID#)	log page	2 of 4
Time	Run id	Alt/FL	Mirr Pos	Int Times		Remarks	
				Vis	NIR		

125635						Start Dark View	*6° offset
125704	P1 ↓	12.2kft	↓ *	75	750	Start Measurement	(AFT) APPLIED
125849	P1 Interrupt	FL110	↓ *	75	750	Interrupt P1. at FL110.	
130410	P1 ↓	FL110	↓ *	75	750	Resume P1. ↓	SWS TEMP +11°C
130831						Start Dark View	East of
130849	P1 ↓	FL657	↓ *	250	750	Start Measurement	In cloud now (thick)
							low spectral energy now. (< 10k counts, but occul peaks to ~25k).
131120	P1 ↓	4.2kft					Still in east of cloud, can view sea surface at times now.
131253						Start Dark Cal	
131320	P1 ↓		↓ *	500	1000	Start Measurement	[CPI NOT WORKING]
		(2.6kft) 1013					
1315	P1	2000'	↓ *	500	1000	Interrupt P1.	
131721	P1 ↓	2000'				Restart P1.	
131933		1.2kft				Start Dark Cal	[TEMP +11°C]
131938	P1	600'	↓ *	1000	1000	Start Measurement	
132141	End P1	(0.8kft) 1013	↓	1000	1000	End P1 at 250'	[CPI still out]
	Start R1	250'	↓			Start R1 at 250'	
132415						Changed ↓ to ↑ (zenith view).	
132456						Start Dark View	(SWS TEMP +11°C)
132526	R1	250'	↑ *	250	1000	Start Measurement	(SWS TEMP +11°C)
						Start Dark View	(SWS TEMP +11°C) *6° offset (to fore)
132944	End R1	250'	↑ *	100	750	Start Measurement	APPLIED.
		(8 mins)					SWS TEMP +11°C
133137	Start P2	250'	↑ *	100	750	Start P2 ↑	
133423						Start Dark View	
133448		(2.7kft) 1013				Start Measurement	
133452		(2.9kft) 1013				Now into spiral ascent.	
1335	P2	(2.9kft) 1013	↑ *	150	750	Into cloud	
133723							[CPI now on OK]
133830		(7.1kft)				CPI seeing ice now	
133923			↑ *	250	1000	Start Dark View	
133952	P2 ↑	7.8kft (1013 sub)				Start Measurement	

[SAMPLE PERIOD = 1.0 sec]

SWS FLIGHT LOG SHEET

Flight #	B 144	Date	3/2/05	Operator(s)	JK (JDL)	log page	3 of 4
Time	Run id	Alt/FL	Mirr Pos	Int Times		Remarks	
				Vis	NIR		

134117	P2 ↗	5.4kft (1013)	↑*	250	1000	Interrupt P2 spiral	* 6° OFFSET (FORE) XPT 100
134214	P2 ↗	n	↑*	250	1000	Resume P2	[SWS TEMP]
134325						Convert to 1000' min ↗	[+11°C]
134749						Start Dark Current view	
134815	P2 ↗	11.1kft.	↑*	150	1000	Start Measurement	
134921	P2	FL120	↑*	150	1000	Interrupt P2	
135008	P2	FL120	↑*	150	1000	Resume spiral P2.	
355 off						Interrupt P2, then resume P2.	
140100	P2 ↗	FL220	↑*	150	1000	Head thinking above; rotate camera view thro' 180° (still looking ↑ to zenith)	
140422	End P2 / Start P3	FL245	↑*	150	1000		
1406			→				←
1							
1407	End P3	FL260		150	1000	End P3 [Turn ↑ to ↓ NAUSIC view]	
140820		FL260	↓*			Start Dark Current View: @ 6° offset	
140848			↓*	100	750	Start Measurement (To AFT)	
140925	Start R2.1	FL260	↓*	100	750	Start R2.1 (STL)	
141058						Deal with #1 spins. [SWS TEMP] Send data looks OK [+12°C]	
(1417-1419)			←			(CAMERA HEAD CABLE LOOSE FROM sensor)	
1419						Start Dark current view ← REFITTED OK	
141938	End R2.1	FL260	↓*	100	750	End R2.1	
141952			↓*	100	750	Start Measurement ←	
142304	Start R2.2	FL260	↓*	100	750	Start R2.2	[SWS TEMP] [+12°C]
						Generally clear below	
142439			↓*			Start Dark Current View * 6° offset	
142504			↓*	350	1000	Start Measurement (To AFT)	
142873						Start Dark Current View	
142870	R2.2	FL260	↓*	150	1000	Start Measurement	
142925			←			Release Sensor #2 (Wind spd/dir)	
14307			←			End R2.2 (fade start time to back on)	
143430						CPI crashed again, but only for few seconds.	

SWS FLIGHT LOG SHEET

Flight #	B 44	Date	3/12/05	Operator(s)	DKX (Ide)	log page	4 of 4
Time	Run id	Alt/FL	Mirr Pos	Int Times Vis	NIR	Remarks	

143625	P4	FL260	↓*	150	1000	Start P4 Profile Descent (Spiral)	
						(*6° aft offset)	
						(SWS Temp +12°C)	
~1442#6	P4	FL260				Interrupt P4 at FL260	
144320	P4					Resume P4	
144834	P4	FL150				Interrupt P4 at FL150	
145015	P4	FL150				Resume Spiral Descent [+13°C]	
145300	P4	12.0kft		150	1000	Peltiers 142 on also now	
145358						Start Dark Current View	
145425	P4	10.7kft	↓*	350	1000	Start Measurement (Clear below)	
						(most of time)	
				500	1000	Dark Current view	
145635	P4	FL090	↓*		←	Interrupt P4	
				500	1000	Start Measurement	
145857	P4	FL090	↓*	500	1000	Resume P4 [+13°C]	
						[still]	
						[CAMERA HEAD STUCK / FROZEN IN ITS POSITION]	
						[ON BULKHEAD FIBER OPTIC CABLE]	
150158	P4	FL065	↓*	500	1000	Interrupt P4	
150318						← CPI crashed again	
						of last	
						Still generally clear below; vent W.	
150827	P4	FL065	↓*	500	1000	Resume P4	
151040						Change to 500' / min P4 descent rate	
		(1.5kft)	↑	1013		at 500'	
151526	P	1000'				Interrupt P4	
151800						← Change NAIR → [+12°C]	
						ZENITH VIEW	
151846			↑*	350	1000	Start Dark Current View	
151911	P4	1000'	↑*	"	"	Start Measurement [+11°C]	
						Peltiers 142 [off]	
152247	P4	1000'	↑*	350	1000	Resume P4	
		1800'	↑	1013		[*6° offset]	
						[FOLE]	
152414	P4/R3	250'	↑*	350	1000	end P4 / START R3	
153220	R3	250'	↑*	350	1000	end R3 [SST = 12.4°C]	
						[WX conditions poor; cloud to S - HEAD FOR HOME]	
154212						SWS recording stopped [+11°C]	
154635		(3 hr 58 m)				← LAND EXTER	

(18 SS 45)

153303 CAMERA FARE I off 2HR 55 58 m.

Microwave Radiometers FLIGHT LOG		Date	03/12/05	Flight	B144	log pages	3
Operator(s)	Ian Rule		Campaign	Micromix			
Departure	Exeter		Arrival	Exeter			

**System start
MARSS**

Visual pod inspection							
Close 3 SSP circuit breakers							
Close all MARSS circuit breakers							
FERA on				at time	1019 ish		
Temperature controller initial temps	Ch16	°C	Ch 17	°C	Ch18	°C	
Temperature controller set points		54°C		58°C	-20	40°C	
MARSS CPU on				at time	1019 ish		
Initial target temperatures	Hot		Cold				
Target heating							
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***							
Scanning on (LMD box)				at time	1019 ish		
Scan indication		Monitor			Visual		

Deimos

Close all Deimos circuit breakers							
Turn on Deimos CPU							
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***							
Start Deimos Software				at time	1016 ish		
Initial target temperatures	Hot	280 ish	Cold	280 ish			
Target heating							
Scan indication		Monitor			Visual		
Weather	Cloud	4/8 Cb 1/8 Sc 1/8 Ci	Precip	Mod rain at time of ob			
	Surface	wet	Pressure	977mb			
	Other						

System functionality check (after initial system warmup, approx 1 hour)

PC to DRS Time error	$t_{PC}=t_{DRS} + 0$	at time	1112				
Brightness temps 'sensible'	Deimos yes, MARSS ch16 u/s and 17 suspect						
Target temps	MARSS:	Hot	344	Cold	282		
	Deimos:	Hot	344	Cold	289		
Channel gains 'sensible'	Ch1 A (-)	Ch3 A (-)	Ch1 B (-)	Ch3 B (-)			
	47	45	49	46			
	Ch16 (40-44) u/s	Ch17 (45-49)	Ch18 (40-44)	Ch19 (40-44)	Ch20 (44-48)		
		34	37	37	40		

Power changeover

Headset on before start							
Listen to engine start sequence	4, 3, 2, 1.						
LMD off (3 switches, bottom to top)							
Exit Deimos Software (x)							
POWER CHANGEOVER							
LMD on (3 switches, top to bottom)	then pushbutton						
Restart Deimos Software							
System running again						at time	

Flight #	B	Date	Operator(s)	log page	2	of	2
Time	Run id	Alt/FL	Remarks	Sys			
1042			Deimos data came back, looks ok so far, poss coinciding with looking into view port and cleaning water off window? MARSS ch 16 u/s, and ch 17 suspect				
1112			Laptop set to DRS time				
1114			Ch17 back				
1151			Deimos off for power change, back up ok, MARSS ok apart from BT shift at power change (or engine start). Both PC times set to DRS.				
115843			T/o Exeter				
1159			Deimos scan appeared to have stuck, restarted ok 1204				
1210			In climb to FL240, instruments reacting correctly				
1217	In transit	FL240	Not sure about ch 17, it appears to be reading very high for over water, however there is a very thick deck of cloud beneath us...?				
1225		FL240	Cloud free above, solid deck below, IAT= -41, DP= -46, Deimos BT's slowly climbing?				
1235		FL240	Cloud thinning, ch17 BT dropping...				
124625	P1	FL240	Start profile descent				
1248			Really not sure of Deimos data, perhaps there is some ice in the scan head or radiometer (lots of water round scanner pre-flight)				
1249			MARSS data showing an obvious downward shift.				
125849		FL110	Interrupt profile				
130410		FL110	Restart				
131535	P1	2000'	Interrupt				
131721	P1	2000'	Restart				
			Peaks in data correspond to most turbulence				
132141	P1/R1	250'	End P1, start Run 1				
132940	R1	250'	End run				
133137	P2	350	Start profile				
133452	P2		Converting to spiral climb				
1340			All data looks good (as far as I can tell)				
134117	P2		Interrupt spiral				
134211	P2		Restart spiral climb				
134921	P2	FL120	Interrupt spiral				
135008	P2	FL120	Restart spiral				
1355	P2	FL170	Interrupt				
135619	P2	FL170	Restart spiral climb				
140338	P2	FL240	End profile, clear above				
140929	R2.1	FL260	Start run, drop sonde				
141928			End run				
142305	R2.2	FL260	Start run, drop sonde, clear above, DP= -60				
143307	R2.2	FL260	End run				
143625	P4	FL260	Spiral profile descent starts				
144216		FL200	Interrupt				
144320	P4		Restart				
144835	P4	FL150	Interrupt profile				

Flight Manager's Instrument Status Log

Flight No. **B** 144

Date: 3rd December 2005

Instrument	Operated	Instrument	Operated
<u>Navigation</u>		<u>Cloud Physics</u>	
INU	Y	Probes	
XR5M GPS	Y	FFSSP	Y
Cruciform GPS	n	PCASP	Y
Satcom C	Y	2D-P	Y
Satcom H	Y	2D-C	Y
<u>Thermometers</u>		Cloudscope	N
De-Iced Temp	Y	SID 1	Y
Non De-Iced	Y	SID 2	N
Heimann	Y	HVPS	N
<u>Hygrometers</u>		CIP25	N
G. Eastern	Y	CIP100	Y
J. Williams	Y		
Nevzorov	Y		
TWC	Y		
FWVS	Y	Racks:	
<u>Radiometers</u>		INC	N
Upper Clear	Y	CCN / CPC	Y
“ Red	Y	CVI	N
“ Silicon	Y		
“ JO1D	N	<u>Aerosol</u>	
Lower Clear	Y	PSAP	N
“ Red	Y	Nephelometer	N
“ Silicon	Y	Filters	N
“ JO1D	N	AMS	N
<u>Large Radiometers</u>			
TAFTS	Y		
MARSS	Y		
DEIMOS	Y	<u>Others:</u>	
ARIES	y	NIR TDLAS	N
SWS	Y	2BT O3	N
<u>Chemistry</u>		VACC	N
Ozone	Y	PEROXIDE	N
SO2	n	Formaldehyde	N
NOX	Y	ADA	Y
CO	y	CPI	Y
ORAC	N	NOxy	N
PAN	N	PTRMS	N
PERCA	N	Bag Sampling	N
WAS	N	Tube Sampling	N

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B144

Date: 3rd December 2005

Instruments

1. UFC not working on startup. Came online during preflight after camera demist activated and power/titler switches cycled a few times.
2. DFC iris continuously cycling between light and dark.
3. Nevzorov failed halfway through flight. Suspect impact damage to vane.
4. Printer reporting network card error.

Aircraft

Starboard taxi and landing lights inop.

Satcom H Calls

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B144:

Log	Reason
Core Chemistry	pre flight only, unmanned operation on auto calibrate so no In Flight log
CPI	Log only of interest to instrument operator so no copy left with FAAM

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

- 3 x Up/Forward Facing Cameras
- 3 x Down/Rearward Facing Cameras

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

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